

COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIORS OF DELAMINATED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Compressive properties of Composite laminates decrease significantly due to the introduction of interlaminar delaminations. The delaminations are easily formed in the laminate when subjected to impact load, fatigue, etc. owing to its weak interlaminar toughness. Mechanisms of low compressive buckling load of composite laminate with multiple delaminations are studied analytically and experimentally. Rayleigh-Ritz approximation and finite element techniques are used in the analysis. The analytical results explain the experimental ones very well. The considerable loss of compressive strength is well explained by the assumption of the multiple delaminations.

KEYWORDS: Composite; Multiple Delaminations; Buckling; Postbuckling; Compressive strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interlaminar delamination is a typical feature of damages of composite laminate owing to the lack of reinforcement in the thickness direction. The significant loss of compressive strength caused by low velocity impact (Compression After Impact) is said owing to the delaminations left around the impact point. It is one of the most important topics to disclose the mechanisms of the compressive strength reduction due to the delaminations. Chai and Babcock¹⁾ and Shimitses et al²⁾ have studied analytically the buckling and post buckling behavior of composite laminate with a delamination. Wang et. al³⁾ also studied the mechanisms of compressive buckling of delaminated S.M.C. composite under the assumption of symmetric deformation. However, the low buckling load obtained was not global panel

instability but only local delamination instability. In the present report, the causes of the drop of the global instability load are studied by considering the existence of multiple equally spaced delaminations.

2. EXPERIMENT

The plain woven fabric glass fiber reinforced composite panels (16 plies, $E_L=20.2$ GPa, $E_T=21.0$ GPa, $\nu_{LT}=0.16$, $G_{LT}=4.1$ GPa) with equally spaced multiple delaminations are prepared for the experiment. The delaminated portions have equal elastic properties. The delaminations are introduced by placing two thin teflon sheets each at the interlaminar planes. The numbers of delaminations are three and seven. The coupon specimens, as shown in Figure 1, are cut from the panels. The delamination lengths studied are listed in Table 1.

Figure 1. Specimen

Table 1 Specimens prepared and the thicknesses (mm).

N	c (mm)				
	10	20	40	60	80
0	(3.68)				
4	3.71	3.80	3.83	3.77	3.78
8	3.71	3.72	3.85	3.72	3.75

The specimen is set in a test machine (Shimadzu, autograph 10-TB) and pushed very slowly with the cross-head speed of 0.1 mm/minute as shown in Figure 2. The deflections at the centers of the both sides of the specimen are measured by using non-contact displacementmeter (Emic, NPA-100) with a special attention in order not to disturb the deformations because the delaminated strips are very thin and sensitive to lateral force. The test data are memorized by using personal computer and analyzed after the experiments.

Figure 2. Test setup

3. Analysis

A composite laminate containing $N-1$ delaminations in the interlaminar areas as shown in Figure 3 is considered. The basic equation is derived based on the Rayleigh-Ritz approximation technique. The Bernoulli-Euler hypothesis is assumed even in the vicinities of the delamination fronts. The both ends are clamped and boundary conditions are written as

$$v_0 = v_0' = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$u_0(L) - u_0(0) = \Delta u \quad (2)$$

where u and v are displacements in x and y directions, The symbol ($'$) denotes the differentiation with respect to x and the suffix 0 following u and v refers the undelaminated base portion and Δu is end-shortening.

The continuity conditions at the delamination fronts are

$$v_I = v_0, \quad v_I' = v_0' \quad (3)$$

$$u_I - y_I v_0' = u_0 \quad (4)$$

where the suffix I ($I=1,2,\dots,N$) refers the delaminated portion I and y_I is the position of neutral axis of I -th delaminated portion.

Figure 3. Analytical model

Total strain energy U is expressed with inplane strains ε_I and curvatures $\kappa_I = -v_I'$ of each portion I as

$$\begin{aligned}
 U &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{L_1} \{A_0 \varepsilon_0^2 + D_0 \kappa_0^2\} dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_{L_2}^L \{A_0 \varepsilon_0^2 + D_0 \kappa_0^2\} dx + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{I=1}^N \int_{L_1}^{L_2} \{A_I \varepsilon_I^2 + D_I \kappa_I^2\} dx \\
 &= \frac{L}{2} \{A_0 \varepsilon_0^2 + \alpha \sum_{I=1}^N A_I \bar{\varepsilon}_I^2\} + \frac{1}{2} [D_0]_0^L \kappa_0^2 dx + \sum_{I=1}^N \int_{L_1}^{L_2} \{D_I \kappa_I^2 - D_0 \kappa_0^2\} dx \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\alpha = (L_2 - L_1)/L = \alpha_2 - \alpha_1 \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_I = \varepsilon_I - \varepsilon_0$$

The coefficients A_0 , D_0 , A_I and D_I are inplane and bending stiffnesses of base portion and I -th delaminated portion, respectively. It is considered that the inplane strains ε_I are constant along the x -axis. From the equilibrium of axial force, the following relation is satisfied.

$$\sum_{I=1}^N A_I \bar{\varepsilon}_I = 0$$

Because no external load is given, the work done by external forces is zero in the present problem. By integrating the strain-displacement relation $\varepsilon = u' + \frac{1}{2} v'^2$ for finite deflection, the end-shortening Δu is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta u = & \varepsilon_0 L + \bar{\varepsilon}_I (L_2 - L_1) + y_I [v_0']_{L_1}^{L_2} \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L v_0'^2 dx - \frac{1}{2} \int_{L_1}^{L_2} \{v_I'^2 - v_0'^2\} dx \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

After some manipulations, the strains ε_0 and $\bar{\varepsilon}_I$ are expressed with the end-shortening Δu and deflection v_I .

$$\begin{aligned} L \varepsilon_0 = & \Delta u + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L v_0'^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{I=1}^N \frac{A_J}{A_0} \int_{L_1}^{L_2} \{v_I'^2 - v_0'^2\} dx \\ & - \left(\sum_{I=1}^N \frac{A_I}{A_0} y_I \right) [v_0']_{L_1}^{L_2} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha L \bar{\varepsilon}_I = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{J=1}^N \left(\delta_{IJ} - \frac{A_J}{A_0} \right) \int_{L_1}^{L_2} v_J'^2 dx - \left(\sum_{J=1}^N \frac{A_J}{A_0} y_J - y_I \right) [v_0']_{L_1}^{L_2} \quad (9)$$

If the laminate is symmetric about the mid surface, the term $\sum_{I=1}^N A_I y_I$ is zero. The total strain energy is expressed only with the deflection v .

The deflection v is developed with the global mode functions $\phi_m(\xi)$, which satisfy the clamped boundary conditions at both ends, and local mode functions $\hat{\phi}_m(\xi)$, which satisfy the zero displacement and slope conditions at the delamination front.

$$v_0 = H q_m \phi_m(\xi) \quad (10)$$

$$v_I = H q_m \phi_m(\xi) + H q_m^{(I)} \hat{\phi}_m(\xi)$$

where

$$\phi_m(\xi) = \cos\{\pi(m-1)\xi\} - \cos\{\pi(m+1)\xi\} \quad (11)$$

$$\hat{\phi}_m(\xi) = \begin{cases} \cos\{\pi(m-1)\eta\} - \cos\{\pi(m+1)\eta\} & 0 < \eta < 1 \\ 0 & \eta < 0, 1 < \eta \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

$$\xi = x/L, \quad \eta = (\xi - \alpha_1)/\alpha$$

Summation convention rule is used about the sum of generalized coordinate for convenience.

By substituting Eq.(10) into the total strain energy, we have the following expression.

$$\bar{U} = \left(\frac{H^2}{D_0} \right) \left\{ A_0 S_0^2 + \sum_{I=1}^N A_I S_I^2 \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + q_m q_n \left\{ \int_0^1 \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi - \sum_{I=1}^N \left(\frac{H_I}{H} - \frac{D_I}{D_0} \right) \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi \right\} \\
& + \sum_{I=1}^N 2q_m^{(I)} q_n \frac{D_I}{D_0} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi + \sum_{I=1}^N q_m^{(I)} q_n^{(I)} \frac{D_I}{D_0} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi \quad (13)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
S_0 = \varepsilon_0 / \left(\frac{H}{L} \right)^2 & = - \frac{3}{\pi^2} B - q_m \left\{ \sum_{I=1}^N \frac{A_I y_I}{A_0 H} [\hat{\phi}_m'(\alpha_2) - \hat{\phi}_m'(\alpha_1)] \right\} \\
& + \frac{1}{2} q_m q_n \int_0^1 \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi + \sum_{I=1}^N \left\{ \frac{A_I}{A_0} q_m^{(I)} q_n \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi + q_m^{(I)} q_n^{(I)} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi \right\} \quad (14)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha S_I = \alpha \varepsilon_I / \left(\frac{H}{L} \right)^2 & = q_m \left\{ \left(\sum_{J=1}^N \frac{A_J y_J}{A_0 H} - \frac{y_J}{H} \right) [\hat{\phi}_m'(\alpha_2) - \hat{\phi}_m'(\alpha_1)] \right\} \\
& + \sum_{J=1}^N \left(\delta_{IJ} - \frac{A_J}{A_0} \right) \left\{ q_m^{(J)} q_n \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi + \frac{1}{2} q_m^{(J)} q_n^{(J)} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} \hat{\phi}_m' \hat{\phi}_n' d\xi \right\} \quad (15)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$B = \Delta u / (\pi^2 H^2 / 3L^2). \quad (16)$$

The basic equation is obtained by differentiating the total potential energy, that is, the total strain energy in the present problem, by the generalized coordinates q_m and $q_m^{(I)}$. The buckling equation is derived by neglecting higher terms of Eq.13 and symbolically written as

$$[K] - B[Q] = 0 \quad (17)$$

4. Results and Discussion

Nondimensional buckling loads obtained from the analysis and the experiment are plotted in Figures 4 and 5. Three typical buckling modes which are obtained from the Rayleigh-Ritz approximation are sketched in Figure 6. They are delamination-closing symmetric (A) and delamination-closing antisymmetric (B) and delamination-opening local modes (C). The antisymmetric buckling load becomes smaller than symmetric one when $0.22 < \alpha < 0.4$ for $N=4$ and when $0.23 < \alpha < 0.28$ for $N=8$ from the Rayleigh-Ritz approximation. The buckling load of local delamination-opening mode is always higher than the symmetric one. The opening mode, however, was observed in the case of long delamination specimens of both $N=4$ and 8. The buckling load obtained from finite element analysis also plotted in the Figure 4. The results are considerably lower than the Rayleigh-Ritz analysis when the delamination is not long. It means that local deformation around delamination tip plays important rolls in the buckling behavior of the delaminated panel. The buckling load suddenly drops when the delamination

length reaches a value ($\alpha=0.25$ for $N=4$ and $\alpha=0.1$ for $N=8$). The sudden drop is caused by antisymmetric buckling in the case of $N=4$.

The load-deflection curves obtained from the experiments are plotted in Figures 7 and 8. The specimen without a delamination buckles at about 2000N in asymmetric shape as expected. The deflection at the center of the specimen of $N=4$ and $\alpha=1/4$ increases little after buckling owing to the antisymmetric deformation and the delaminations gradually opens. The specimen of $N=8$ and $\alpha=1/2$ buckles in delamination opening mode at very low load (about 1/30 of specimen without a delamination). The delamination-opening was also observed in the postbuckling of antisymmetric mode in the case of the specimens with medium length delaminations. The delamination opening seems to be very important factor for the failure, which was initiated by the delamination propagation. The experimental results agree well with those from the Rayleigh-Ritz method and excellent with those from the finite element method.

5. CONCLUSION

From the present analytical and experimental study, we have the following conclusion.

- (1) Very efficient analytical method to predict the overall buckling phenomena of delaminated composite panel is proposed. However, finite element analysis is necessary to obtain precise results.
- (2) The significant reduction of the compressive strength of the composite panel owing to the interlaminar delaminations can be explained by assuming the multiple delaminations.
- (3) Compressive buckling stress suddenly starts to decrease when delaminations reach a certain length.
- (4) Antisymmetric mode must not be neglected when the buckling behavior of delaminated panels are considered.
- (5) Although the buckling load of delamination-opening local mode is not smallest, delamination opening is observed in the postbuckling and plays important rolls in the final failure which is triggered by the delamination instability.

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Figure 4. Buckling load and delamination length (N=4)
 — ○ ◇ symmetric mode, ---- ● ◆ antisymmetric mode

Figure 5. Buckling load and delamination length (N=8)
 — ○ symmetric mode, ---- ● antisymmetric mode

(A) Symmetric delamination-closing mode

(B) Antisymmetric delamination-closing mode

(C) Symmetric delamination-opening mode

(D) Mode observed in postbuckling

(E) Mode observed in postbuckling

Figure 6. Typical buckling modes (A), (B) and (C) and deflection mode observed in the postbuckling (D) and (E)

Figure 8. Relation between load and deflection ($N=8$)

Biography

The author was born in 1952. Bachelor in 1975 from Department of Aeronautics, University of Tokyo. Master of Engineering in 1977 and Doctor of Engineering in 1980 also from Department of Aeronautics, University of Tokyo. Research associate of Institute of Interdisciplinary Research, University of Tokyo from 1980 to 1986. Visiting assistant professor of Department of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics, University of Illinois from 1983 to 1985. Associate Professor of Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sophia University since 1986.